

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for **African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.**

D3.4 Inventory of capacity building resources and ready to use training material

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Glossary and Abbreviations

DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
PPT	PowerPoint
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The work package (WP) 3 of the AfriConEU project aims to design and develop the AfriConEU Networking Academy and its two flagship programmes on Capacity Building for African DIHs and Partnership Building between African and European DIHs. A series of subprogrammes will be designed to meet the needs of the African DIH, as well as promote Africa-Europe collaborations.

This WP is, then, dedicated to the creation of the two Flagship Programmes in terms of content and structure development, as well as in terms of the tools that will be utilized for delivering them. The AfriConEU Networking Academy, through its two flagship programmes, will therefore provide resources, knowledge sharing and joint project development opportunities to African and European DIHs as well as other stakeholders of the digital economy including the African Diaspora Communities.

Furthermore, for the development of these sub-programmes, partners will utilize existing knowledge and lessons learned as well as content from other training programmes developed for DIHs both in Africa and Europe. In fact, existing capacity building programmes for DIHs were previously identified and further scanned (see D2.2 - Online database with DIHs Capacity Building programmes), and the most appropriate contents were selected for further elaboration, adaptation, and localisation to meet African DIHs needs.

1. Objective of the Inventory

The objective of the inventory is to provide open access to the above mentioned resources, as well as to allow access by organising the items in three categories: online courses, webinars and material.

The Inventory of Training Resources is available at <https://africoneu.eu/training-resources/> in the AfriConEU website, within the tab Library (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Location of the Inventory within the AfriConEU website

2. Inventory categories

The Inventory of Training Resources, as mentioned above, is organised in three main categories: Online Courses, Webinars, Materials (Figure 2). It includes training resources on several topics such as Business, Management, Marketing, Artificial Intelligence, Start-up ecosystem, Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH), among others. The selected themes and topics took into consideration the identified needs of the DIH made in the scope of WP2 - Context and state of the art analysis, of the project.

Figure 2 - Categories of the Inventory of Training Resources

For the development of the AfriConEU Flagship Programmes, the goal is to use tools, training contents and resources already developed in other capacity-building programmes – the intention is to reuse and re-adapt training resources and develop standardised capacity building material, rather than content development. Training resources include, but are not limited to, PowerPoint presentations, videos, case studies, readings, webinars, etc. Some examples are presented Figure 3 and in Table 1.

Figure 3 - List training materials available in the AfriConEU Inventory (content detail)

Table 1 – Examples of training resources available in the AfriConEU Inventory

Type	Existing material	Programme in which will be used
Webinar	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LjvYsL3Gv_E&ab_channel=L.Team	Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women, particularly in the “Collaborate to innovate” part.
Worksheet	https://smartfactories.eu/uploads/7b848e7ce7c6a2a9222acbfa4a18577a3fcd7019.xlsx	Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women, particularly in the “Purpose-driven DIH” part.
PPT for Webinar	https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/library/reports-resources/Presentations/2020-0131-SAH-how-to-develop-a-DIH_M-Butter-1580481436.pdf	Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women, particularly in the “Purpose-driven DIH” part.
Webinar	https://youtu.be/KqIUBKiqvUE	Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women, particularly in the “Purpose-driven DIH” part.
Webinar	https://spaces.fundingbox.com/spaces/dihnet-eu-digital-	Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women, particularly in the “Collaborate to innovate” part.
PPT for Webinar	https://dihworld.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Webinar-20-July_PwC_v1.0-1.pdf	Capacity building in technology transfer of innovative technologies (IoT, AI, Big data, etc.).
Module	https://smartagrihubs.curatr3.com/courses/dih-exchange/home#level/232328	Capacity building in business development models and multi-actor approach

3. Inventory updating

Besides the topics already referred, additional ones will be included based on the interests of the participants of the AfriConEU target audience. All partners will seek to continuously update the AfriConEU Inventory by sharing new material and training resources. All materials included in the AfriConEU Inventory of Training Resources will be accessible for free to the interested stakeholders and webpage visitors.

The updating of the Inventory of Training Resources will be simultaneous with the delivery of the capacity building activities planned within the Flagship Programmes, as trainers and speakers will be also invited to add significant resources.